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ABSTRACT: The article the activities of teachers aimed, at developing children's memory. While there have been significant theoretical advances in child neuropsychology in recent years, progress in clinical practice has been restricted owing to a lack of well standardized, developmentally appropriate assessment techniques This paper addresses this issue, with the focus on memory and learning skills These abilities are targeted because they are frequently impaired following brain damage in childhood, and because they are of central importance to the efficient acquisition of cognitive, educational and social skills throughout childhood Using a normative sample of 376 children, aged 7 0 to 13 11 years, the paper describes the range of memory and learning skills in childhood, and interprets progress in these skills with reference to neurological and cognitive theory.

KEYWORDS: memory, educational and cognitive activity, learning process, verbal and logical memory, involuntary memorization.

INTRODUCTION: The memory can be defined as the ability to receive, store and reproduce information.

The relevance of the topic due to the fact that the memory is the basis of the child's abilities, is the condition for learning, acquiring knowledge and skills, ie the memory of the younger schoolboy - the paramount psychological component of teaching and learning activities. Teacher needs to build the learning process so as to achieve the maximum memory material and its student's the most accurate reproduction, and this is possible only when the psychological processes become arbitrary.

The process of development of memory in children will proceed successfully if the teacher and parents will build it, taking into account the individual characteristics of a particular child. Using the recommendations, use different methods of promoting good memorization.

1 Younger school age child is called the vertex. The child retains many qualities of childhood - carelessness, naivety, look at the adult from the bottom up. At this age, children are very strong focus on children outside world. Facts, events, details make them a strong

impression. An important source of success in the teaching of younger students - their imitation. Students repeat the teacher's reasoning, give examples of similar examples companions, etc. In connection with entering school there is a significant restructuring and development of the children's memory. Memory is gradually becoming more organized, regulated and controlled mental activity. memory processes increasingly take on the character of arbitrary processes gradually developed and improved verbal and logical memory

2 As a speech and language therapist I come across younger and older children who struggle with classroom-oriented tasks in school. When assessed by specialists, a good proportion of these children are found to have working memory difficulties. Working memory is responsible for retention and manipulation of information. As children get older, the learning-based tasks in school become more structured and complex, demanding high cognitive skills. Therefore, working memory plays a crucial role in determining children's ability to handle learning challenges effectively. At home or in other social situations outside school, the environment is more play-based and relaxed and so the demands on working memory are likely to be less. Working memory is one of the key cognitive processes required for effective learning and is often confused with short term memory. Short term memory is related to short-term storage of information. Whereas, according to recent research, working memory is a component of fluid reasoning i.e. ability to effectively identify key information from the task/environment and apply that knowledge. We use our working memory to register, maintain and manipulate information we see (visual) and hear (auditory) making it an integral part in our decision-making ability and behavior. Therefore, we can see how working memory skills can be closely related to achievement and learning in school aged children.

The Wechsler Intelligence Scale for Children (WISC) measures working memory in one of its subtests for measuring intelligence. However, we should bear in mind that although working memory affects how a child learns and performs in tests, it is not a measure of a child's overall intelligence and that the IQ (Intelligent Quotient) also has non-measurable components which do not correlate to working memory.

CONCLUSION: It is very important in the testing and correction of the child's memory to orient more on semantic memory and show your child a variety of techniques to help you better remember that or other material.

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